

“Trends in Image reconstruction in 2020”

**International Journal of Computational Science and
Information Technology (IJCSITY)**

ISSN : 2320-7442 (Online) ; 2320 - 8457 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsity/index.html>

MULTIPLE RECONSTRUCTION COMPRESSION FRAMEWORK BASED ON PNG IMAGE

Zhiqing Lu and Jin Tang

Key Lab of Intelligent Computing and Signal Processing of Ministry of Education, School of Computer
Science and Technology, Anhui University, Hefei 230601, China

ABSTRACT

It is shown that neural networks (NNs) achieve excellent performances in image compression and reconstruction. However, there are still many shortcomings in the practical application, which eventually lead to the loss of neural network image processing ability. Based on this, a joint framework based on neural network and scale compression is proposed in this paper. The framework first encodes the incoming PNG image information, and then the image is converted into binary input decoder to reconstruct the intermediate state image, next, we import the intermediate state image into the zooming compressor and repressurize it, and reconstruct the final image. From the experimental results, this method can better process the digital image and suppress the reverse expansion problem, and the compression effect can be improved by 4 to 10 times as much as that of using RNN alone, showing better ability in the application. In this paper, the method is transmitted over a digital image, the effect is far better than the existing compression method alone, the Human visual system cannot feel the change of the effect.

KEYWORDS

Neural network · Image compression · Image reconstruction · Scaling of compression

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsity/V7N4/7419ijcsity01.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhao Z, Guan Q, Zhang H, (2018) Improving the Robustness of Adaptive Steganographic Algorithms Based on Transport Channel Matching [J]. IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security, 1-1.
- [2] George Toderici, Sean M. O'Malley, (2016) [Variable Rate Image Compression with Recurrent Neural Networks](#).
- [3] Toderici G, Vincent D, Johnston N, (2016) [Full Resolution Image Compression with Recurrent Neural Networks](#).
- [4] Z. Wang, E. P. Simoncelli, and A. C. Bovik. (2003) [Multiscale structural similarity for image quality assessment](#). In Signals, Systems and Computers, 2004. Conference Record of the Thirty-Seventh Asilomar Conference on, volume 2, pages 1398-1402.
- [5] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber(1997)s Long short-term memory. Neural Computation.
- [6] Toderici G, O'Malley S M , Hwang S J , (2015) [Variable Rate Image Compression with Recurrent Neural Networks](#).
- [7] Xiao-Dong H, Xi-Jian P, Tao Z. (2010) New Detection Algorithm of Double Compression in JPEG Image. Computer Engineering,36(4):140-143.
- [8] Pevny T, Fridrich J. (2008) [Detection of Double-compression in JPEG Images for Application in Steganography](#). IEEE Trans. on Information Forensics and Security,3(2): 247-258. A.D. Ker, P. Bas, et al. (2013) Moving steganography and steganalysis from the laboratory into the real world, in Proceedings of the First ACM Workshop on Information Hiding and Multimedia Security, ser. IH&MMSec pp. 45-58.
- [9] Y. Zhang, X. Luo, et al. (2016) Joint jpeg compression and detection resistant performance enhancement for adaptive steganography using feature regions selection, Multimedia Tools and Applications, pp. 120.
- [10] W. Luo, G. L. Heileman, (2002) [Fast and robust watermarking of jpeg files](#), in Proceedings Fifth IEEE Southwest Symposium on Image Analysis and Interpretation, pp. 158-162.
- [11] Zhang Y, Luo X, (2016) [A framework of adaptive steganography resisting JPEG compression and detection](#) . Security and Communication Networks.
- [12] Y. Zhang, X. Zhu, (2017) Dither modulation based adaptive steganography resisting jpeg compression and statistic detection, Multimedia Tools and Applications.
- [13] Y. Zhang, C. Qin, (2018) [On the fault tolerant performance for a class of robust image steganography, Signal Processing](#), vol. 146, pp. 99-111.
- [14] G. E. Hinton and R. R. Salakhutdinov. (2006) [Reducing the dimensionality of data with neural networks](#). Science, 313(5786):504-507.
- [15] Krizhevsky and G. E. Hinton. (2011) [Using very deep autoencoders for content-based image retrieval](#). In European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks.
- [16] P. Vincent, H. Larochelle, Y. Bengio, (2012) [Extracting and composing robust features with denoising autoencoders](#). Journal of Machine Learning Research.

- [17] Gregor K, Besse F, (2016) Towards Conceptual Compression.
- [18] Soltani R, Jiang H. (2016) Higher Order Recurrent Neural Networks.
- [19] R. K. Srivastava, K. Greff, (2015) Highway networks. In International Conference on Machine Learning: Deep Learning Workshop.
- [20] W. Zaremba, I. Sutskever, (2014) Recurrent neural network regularization.
- [21] Danihelka, G. Wayne, (2016) Associative long short-term memory. In ICML.